

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

[4.1 - Dataset of analysis]

SPOKE N 3 – Tourism and culture industry

DELIVERABLE 4.1

Version history

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Contents

1. Introduction.....	4
2. Activities.....	4
2.1 Borghi Narranti	4
2.2. Green Heritage	10
2.3. AgriFood. Il Made in Italy a portata di mano	15
2.4. Destination Management Organization (DMO) nell'ambito del Piano di Sviluppo Turistico della Grecia Salentina	16
3. Conclusion	18

Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.

Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti s" affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

1. Introduction

Over the past few months (October 2023-May 2024), the University of Salento research team has been testing new theoretical-methodological and operational articulations within projects, workshops and actions that have constituted an important ground for critical observation and experimentation with procedures of analysis and intervention aimed, ultimately, at the valorization of tangible and intangible cultural heritage and the facilitation of heritage processes by communities.

In this sense, the Department of Humanities and Social Sciences, at which almost all faculty, researchers and research fellows involved in the NODES project are incardinated, has played a leading role, inaugurating long-term experiences aimed at innervating the economic context and producing new trajectories of local development and social promotion.

The NODES project, therefore, immediately provided a valuable opportunity to give continuity to a series of initiatives already undertaken, with particular reference to the analysis of the relationships between the environment, territory, tourism, protection of tangible and intangible cultural heritage and the definition of paths of valorization for tourism purposes. Food, from this point of view, is configured as the thematic axis that holds together this constellation of research conducted by Spoke 3 of the NODES project, which sees the Department of Human and Social Sciences of the University of Salento as the lead agency.

Under the supervision of the scientific head of Spoke 3, Prof. Fabio Pollice, Magnificent Rector of the University of Salento, a complex networking action was therefore launched between public and private actors who, in different capacities, share and work for the promotion of a model of valorization of the supply chain that generates wealth and sustainable well-being through the adoption of targeted and multi-scalar policies.

2. Activities

The initiatives and research referred to are detailed below:

2.1 Borghi Narranti

The on field project Borghi Narranti, born from the collaboration between the association “I Borghi più belli d'Italia,” the European University Center for Cultural Heritage of Ravello and the Department of Human and Social Sciences of the University of Salento, started in September 2023, with a preliminary and general reconnaissance of the material and immaterial sediments (desk phase) present in the villages identified as “s-object” of narration: Castagnole delle Lanze (AT), Montagnana (PD), Trevi (PG), Gesualdo (AV), Tropea (VV).

During this first phase, a list was defined, for each village, of sites of interest of an artistic, architectural, environmental, and landscape nature; of local actors; and of practices, traditions, and typical food and craft products that

were evaluated, by the working group, as shared identity sediments, fundamental to the construction of the narrative because of their obvious historical-cultural value for the communities of reference.

This was achieved through a thorough examination of literature (national and local), press, websites (institutional, tourism, travel blogs, etc.) and social media (YouTube, Instagram, Facebook, etc.). Given the visual nature of the final project outputs (visual storytelling), a comparative observation of existing audiovisual products present in open access or on platforms was also undertaken in order to identify, for each village, dominant themes and styles and thus better define a possible original and innovative narrative-film strategy. The collected material was then shared and discussed with the referents of the villages (indicated by the Association "I Borghi più belli d'Italia") and with the stakeholders identified by the working group together with them.

These stakeholders were asked, during the on-site visit, to intervene to guide-through opinions, stories, testimonies-the partial outcomes of the desk survey. In consultation with the village stakeholders, a detailed schedule of filmed interviews was then established for the duration of the survey. Administrators, local producers, cultural workers, restaurateurs, farmers, artisans, sportspeople, artists, and citizens were interviewed and shared with the project staff stories of community life, autobiographical narratives related to place, cultural heritage and daily life, memories and planning. The group of interviewees presents rather heterogeneous characters, both in terms of profession and interests, gender, and age.

The filmed interviews-conducted according to the narrative interview model in order to weave a common, shared and participatory narrative-were recorded on audio-video files and resulted in a filming diary and an audiovisual archive specific to each village, which was drawn on during selection, editing and post-production.

Output of the project is the creation of a website presenting a total of thirty short documentaries that collect voices, faces, interviews, stories, and experiences of the communities regarding typical food and wine, religious and secular celebrations, traditions, memories, customs, craft knowledge, cultural heritage, daily life, crafts, and associations.

In addition, the site presents a series of podcasts: these are fictional tales woven from real stories and historical figures who were born or lived part of their lives in the villages and still represent an identity reference for the communities.

Finally, the tangible and intangible sediments were classified in the format "10 experiences to live," which summarizes, for each hamlet, the activities, typical products, places, anecdotes, and legends that the community feels are indispensable references for the experiential tourist(s) who wish to experience the hamlet with authenticity (fig. 1).

 Borghi narranti

GESUALDO
10 ESPERIENZE DA VIVERE

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| 1 La città del Principe dei musicisti | 6 Tante belle cose |
| 2 Tra i ricordi di Padre Pio | 7 Tra angeli e diavoli |
| 3 Indossare il passato | 8 Ascoltare i madrigali nel castello |
| 4 Col naso all'insù per Kathy Toma | 9 Antiche ricette e giovani promesse |
| 5 L'accio di Gesualdo | 10 Che bel vedere! |

Figura 1 – Example of "10 esperienze da vivere" format

Below are some photographs from the surveys conducted by the research team (figs. 2-6); the drop-down menu on the home page of the Borghi Narranti website (which as of today is in the final stages of set up, prior to publication) (fig. 7); and some previews of the documentary shorts (figs. 8-10).

Figura 2 - Castagnole delle Lanze (20-21-22 ottobre 2023)

Fig. 3 - Montagnana (October 27-28-29, 2023)

Figura 4 - Trevi (10-11-12 novembre 2023)

Fig. 5 - Gesualdo (November 17-18-19, 2023)

Fig. 6 - Tropea (December 8-9-10, 2023)

Fig. 7 – Cascading menu taken from the home page of the Narrating Villages website

Montagnana

A uguale distanza da Padova, Verona e Vicenza, Montagnana è oggi un piccolo borgo dove è possibile ammirare palazzi maestosi e piccole casette di tutti i colori. Ma nel Medioevo era un centro cruciale, per la sua posizione geografica. Montagnana infatti conserva intatte le sue mura da ottocento anni e usando l'immaginazione puoi riuscire a vedere il fossato, il ponte levatoio, i soldati di guardia sulle mura. La attraversiamo con Silvia, una delle guide turistiche del Museo Civico.

Enrico, il capomastro della Bottega artigiana Pesavento a Montagnana, ci accoglie insieme a suo figlio Stefano. E ci racconta delle sue origini cimbre, degli strumenti della tradizione nell'altopiano di Asiago da cui la sua famiglia proviene, dell'importanza di tramandare questo prezioso sapere artigianale. La bottega oggi è gestita dal figlio Stefano, che cerca di innovare partendo sempre da una tradizione che conosce a menadito il legno e nel rispetto degli alberi, in quanto esseri viventi che meritano grande devozione.

Fig. 8 - Previews of documentary shorts featured on the Narrating Villages web site (under construction)

Gesualdo

La memoria dei luoghi risiede anche negli oggetti e nella passione di chi li colleziona. A Gesualdo è possibile trovarne una traccia autentica nella bottega di un rigattiere.

Tropea

La musica popolare calabrese, la tarantella, affonda le sue radici in secolari tradizioni regionali e accompagna tutti i momenti della vita: matrimoni, battesimi e compleanni.

Fig. 9 - Previews of documentary shorts featured on the Narrating Villages web site (under construction)

Trevi

Al suono dei tamburi e avvolti nei colori vivaci dei loro costumi, gli abitanti di Castagnole si uniscono ogni anno all'ottobre trevano, una festa che celebra le radici storiche del XIII e XIV secolo di Trevi. Questo evento non solo rievoca il passato medievale, ma rinnova il senso di coesione e appartenenza della comunità, ravvivando la passione e l'orgoglio per le proprie tradizioni.

Castagnole delle Lanze

L'anfiteatro delle vigne, così viene chiamato questo incredibile panorama tra Langhe e Monferrato, creato nei secoli dall'incessante lavoro di contadini e viticoltori. Adotta anche tu un filare, scopri le fasi della coltura della vigna e degusta il vino Barbera.

Fig. 10 - Previews of documentary shorts featured on the Narrating Villages web site (under construction)

2.2. Green Heritage

The issue of climate change claims public attention on an international scale and is now undoubtedly high on the political agenda. The importance and cogency of the issue, moreover, make it desirable for an increasingly lively and widespread interest among institutions, associations, sector bodies and communities. While it is true that there has

been a lively debate around the environmental, social and economic implications of climate change, it should be noted, however, that some of its less obvious - or at least indirect - implications still remain in the background, awaiting new attention and sensitivity capable of grasping them.

Among these aspects to be explored, there is certainly the impact of climate change on intangible cultural heritage, consisting of practices, rituals, stories, languages, songs, dances, traditions, foods, and skills that communities recognize as fundamental elements in the construction and representation of the collective self. These are cultural traces that, precisely as a result of climate change, have an increasing degree of vulnerability.

Environmental disasters and extreme weather events (floods, fires, high temperatures, droughts), in fact, can have a profound impact on people's lifestyles, agricultural, livestock or production customs, as well as community traditions, customs and practices. It is, moreover, noteworthy that it is precisely communities that are the ultimate custodians and preservers of intangible cultural heritage and that they often lack the skills, tools and strategies useful for mitigating its negative effects.

With this in mind, the project "Green Heritage. The impact of climate change on the Intangible Heritage," an Erasmus+ project funded by the European Union, which over the course of three years (December 2022 to November 2025) and in synergy with professionals, educational centers, administrations, local stakeholders and civil society aims to study how and how much climate change may pose a risk to intangible cultural heritage. The aim is to develop a holistic, innovative and inclusive approach to observing and assessing the direct and indirect impacts of climate change on intangible cultural heritage. Among the aims of the Green Heritage project, are a series of actions, including a preliminary analysis of climate change adaptation needs and practices in the European Union and partner countries; the creation of synergies between cross-sectoral researchers, practitioners, policy makers and citizens in order to bring knowledge into dialogue and discuss the most appropriate measures for the management and preservation of intangible heritage; and an interactive map illustrating the areas and regions most at risk in Europe. Thus, within the Green Heritage project, innovative training tools and methodologies are being experimented with that can promote adaptive and systemic approaches for better impact management even on those cultural sediments to which collective action and political debate have so far not given due attention and which instead represent, on closer inspection, precious treasure chests for the identity of communities, for their history and also for their development.

Final project outputs include a set of tools and operational methods for impact analysis and a well cadenced schedule of policy round tables within which to discuss what emerges from community dialogues and spatial analysis.

The consortium bringing Green Heritage to life consists of the following partners: National Research Council (IT); CUEBC European University Center for Cultural Heritage (IT); CMCC Euro-Mediterranean Center Foundation on Climate Change (IT); ReadLab P.C. Laboratory for Research, Innovation and Development (GR); ILFA LU Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art of the University of Latvia (LV); UAEGEAN University of the Aegean (GR); CANDIDE International (BE), ELORIS S.A. Society for Research, Education, Innovation and Development of the North Aegean Region (GR); ALLI Athens Lifelong Learning Institute (GR) (fig. 11). The project is co-funded by the European Union, through the Erasmus+ program.

Partner network

(Belgio, Grecia, Italia, Lettonia, Spagna)

Figura 11 - Partners network Green Heritage project

On April 12 and 13, 2024, a policy round table was held in Ravello by the European University Center for Cultural Heritage in the presence of experts, technicians, and community representatives (fig. 12).

Specifically, the European University Center for Cultural Heritage invited experts, local administrators, research organizations, businesses, and associations to dialogue and discuss within the framework of two round tables:

- Knowledge and Techniques

The art of dry stone walls on the Amalfi Coast

The Amalfi Coast represents an exceptionally valuable example of this traditional building technique. The particular geological and natural characteristics of the area, in fact, combined with the community's profound knowledge of the environments and natural and climatic phenomena, has meant that, over the centuries, the technique of dry stone walls was developed to pursue a balance between human needs and nature. These learned and passed down knowledge, however, are threatened due to climate change. Among the most obvious effects are certainly the heavy rains and long droughts that affect the outcome of harvests and affect, in addition, the precarious balance of dry stone walls, causing them to first swell and then collapse, generating stone landslides downstream.

- Traditions, Rituals and Cults

The feast of the Madonna Avvocata, one of the most heartfelt festivals and celebrations of the intangible heritage of the Amalfi Coast, which also plays an important role in terms of raising the awareness of the local community in relation to the maintenance and management of the site, including the dry stone wall system. This is a very ancient and complex ritual, consisting of a pilgrimage that takes place once a year, a procession that

follows the waterways in the area, and a final celebration. Interviews conducted as part of the Green Heritage project have shown how climate change is directly affecting pilgrimages, processions and celebrations. This is not only due to the damaging effects of heavy rains that cause paths to slip, but also to severe drought that deprives springs and the large cistern next to the church at the top of the mountain of water. In addition, climate change, combined with the abandonment of the fields, leads to a gradual collapse of the terraced system of dry stone walls and destroys the ancient paths in many places, effectively blocking the ascent to the mountain. This entails the risk that pilgrims can no longer climb to the Sanctuary of the Avvocata from the Maiori side.

- Festa dei Ceri di Gubbio: The Festa dei Ceri in Gubbio (Umbria), due to its historicity making it one of the oldest and most popular ritual festivals in Italy, as evidenced by the “Tavolette Iguvine,” dating back to the 3rd-1st century BC. The Festa dei Ceri takes place in Gubbio on May 15 each year and consists of the running transport of three Ceri crowned with statues of saints: St. Ubaldo (Patron Saint of Gubbio), St. George and St. Anthony Abbot. Gubbio and its cultural heritage, therefore, represent a case of exceptional interest, creating a connection between the tangible and intangible nature of cultural heritage. The importance and popularity of the event at the regional level is such that since 1973 the three Ceri have been the symbol of the Region of Umbria and appear in its banner and official flag. In Gubbio, it seems very clear, however, that weather conditions have changed dramatically in recent decades. Temperatures in Gubbio from 2011 to 2021 show a clear linear growth. Similarly, a worrying positive trend in precipitation is observed. Extreme weather events could produce structural instabilities due to hydrogeological problems for the entire historic area, as evidenced by existing slow and progressive deformations and cracking patterns affecting ancient structures. This could also produce damage to the roads where the unbridled running of the “Festa dei Ceri” takes place and landslides on the mountain.

The three case studies discussed at the policy round table are part of a broader corollary of cases being examined throughout Europe. During the desk phase, in fact, 14 case studies were identified as significant examples useful both to observe and monitor for each of the partner countries (Greece, Italy, Latvia, and Spain) the situation regarding the awareness of political actors and communities about the impact of CC on CH, and to draw new interpretative categories of the phenomenon and study possible risk mitigation strategies.

The list of case studies is shown below:

- CS 1: Puffin gathering and hunting (Denmark)
- CS 2: Mountaineering (France, Italy, Switzerland)
- CS 3: Wine culture in Germany
- CS 4: Agricultural and food traditions of the carob tree in Crete (UAEGEAN)
- CS 5: Mandras (Paddocks) of Lemnos (UAEGEAN)
- CS 6: Traditional Practices of Wild Edible Plants in Crete (UAEGEAN)
- CS 7: Art of dry stone walls, knowledge and techniques in the Cinque Terre and the Amalfi Coast (CUEBC and CMCC)

- CS 8: Festa dei Ceri / Corsa dei Ceri - Gubbio (CNR)
- CS 9: Feast of the Madonna Avvocata (Amalfi Coast, CUEBC)
- CS 10: Network of large shoulder processional structures (CUEBC)
- CS 11: Lamprey fishing and preparation skills in Carnikava (ILFA)
- CS 12: Natural ice skating (Netherlands)
- CS 13: Transhumance in the Cantabrian or Northern Third of Spain (FSMLR)
- CS 14: Valencian Paella, the Art of Uniting and Sharing (FSMLR)

Beginning with the discussion of the three Italian case studies, therefore, we reflected on possible forms of vulnerability of intangible cultural heritages in the face of climate change, risk mitigation strategies, and before that, useful actions to generate awareness and proactivity among communities.

The work led to the development of this policy brief, containing general guidelines and recommendations for preventing the effects of climate change on intangible cultural heritage.

The policy brief represents the fruit of work marked by listening and dialogue among experts, professionals and communities who shared expertise and experience. This has produced a document addressed to local, regional, national and European governments, containing a series of recommendations aimed at guiding decision-making processes in this field. In any case, the document may arouse the interest of anyone interested in the topic and its implications. A fundamental aspect of the project is, in fact, that relating to the communication and sharing of research results since, among its main objectives, there is the development of new awareness both within the communities of reference of the case studies and other communities that present the same vulnerabilities, associations, sector bodies, and foundations.

A set of policies to focus on in the medium and long term emerged from the work. These are general and specific recommendations that aim to promote concrete and strategic actions to safeguard and

protect intangible cultural heritage in the context of current challenges arising from climate change.

The general recommendations have been divided into ten macro-themes: a) involvement of local communities and stakeholders working in the intangible cultural heritage sector; b) regulation; c) governance and planning of risk management interventions; d) education and training; e) information and awareness; f) preservation and management; g) supporting tangible and intangible infrastructure; h) targeted research/actions; i) capitalization and capitalization of values and best practices of events, l) green solutions for events part of intangible cultural heritage.

Fig. 12 - Policy round table Green Heritage project (Ravello, April 12 and 13, 2024)

2.3. AgriFood. Il Made in Italy a portata di mano

The conference AgriFood. Made in Italy at your fingertips was held on May 9, 2024, at the University of Salento. It was part of a series of events supporting traditional Made in Italy supply chains, where a specific forum on Economies was planned (Fig. 13).

A driving sector for the Apulia Region, Agrifood is among the most relevant and dynamic sectors of Made in Italy, which for this reason called to reaffirm its ability to address with vision and innovation the profound transformations taking place, with respect to the discontinuities of the macroeconomic scenario, the energy crisis, climate change and ongoing war conflicts. In the initiative, experts and entrepreneurs from the sector were involved to stimulate discussion and identify viable development strategies.

Fig. 13 - Conference "Agrifood. Il Made in Italy a portata di mano" (Mau 9, 2024 - University of Salento)

Il Made in Italy a portata di mano

#ItalianEXPerience
Un ciclo di eventi a supporto delle filiere tradizionali del Made in Italy

FORUM DELLE ECONOMIE
Food EXPerience

Giovedì, 9 maggio 2024
16:00-17:00

Università del Salento - Rettorato
Piazza Tarantini, 7, 73100

Settore trainante per la Regione Puglia, l'AgriFood è tra i comparti più rilevanti e dinamici del **Made in Italy**, attualmente e ancor di più, è chiamato a rafforzare la propria capacità di affrontare con visione e innovazione le profonde trasformazioni in atto, rispetto alle discontinue, dello scenario macroeconomico, della crisi energetica, dei cambiamenti climatici e dei conflitti bellici in corso.

UniCredit rilancia il dibattito sulle prospettive e sulle opportunità del comparto AgriFood con un Forum dedicato. L'incontro rientra nelle iniziative di UniCredit per l'Italia a supporto delle imprese nei settori tradizionali del Made in Italy. Saranno coinvolti esperti ed imprenditori del comparto, per stimolare il confronto e individuare strategie di sviluppo percorribili.

In collaborazione con:

AGENDA

10:00 Welcome coffee - accredito partecipanti

10:30 **Avvenire lavori**
Fabio Polacco Rettore Università del Salento
Carlo Salsani Sindaco di Lecce
Angela Ricchiuto Vice Presidente Confindustria Lecce
Fernando Nestali Regional Manager - Sud UniCredit

10:50 **Andrea Dossena** Associate Partner Prometeia
"La transizione della filiera AgriFood: sostenibilità e mercato"

11:10 **Alessandro Tozi** Referente AgriBusiness Corporate Italy UniCredit
Sergio Olivadese Referente Turismo Corporate Italy UniCredit
"Il rapporto di UniCredit ai settori dell'AgriFood e del Turismo e le loro connessioni"

11:20 **Tavola rotonda: "I fattori di crescita dell'AgriFood. Innovazione, sostenibilità e innovazione. Riflessioni sul futuro prossimo"**
Alessandro De Mita Direttore Generale Puglia Sviluppo
Stefano Leo Export Manager Cantine Pasticcio Srl
Nicco Martinuzzi Direttore Commerciale Martinuzzi Srl
Fernando Nestali Regional Manager Sud UniCredit
Vico Michele Paradiso Direttore Università del Salento
Modena, Alessandro Tozi Referente AgriBusiness Corporate Italy UniCredit

12:10 **Tavola rotonda: "Valorizzazione delle eccellenze territoriali. Una diretta connessione tra AgriFood, Turismo, Cultura e Sostenibilità"**
Massimiliano Apollonio Presidente Mov. Turismo del Vino
Sergio Dimitri ESG Expert Sud UniCredit
Luca Forte Amministratore Delegato Dropan Spa
Sara Nocco Docente Università del Salento
Fabio Polacco Rettore Università del Salento
Domenico Scordari CEO N&B Natural is Better Srl
Francesco Vena CEO Luciano 1894 Srl
Moderatore: Leandro Sansone Responsabile Territorial Development Sud UniCredit

13:00 Chiusura lavori. Seguirà light lunch

Empowering Communities to Progress. UniCredit

Fig. 14 - Event program "AgriFood. Il Made in Italy a portata di mano"

2.4. Destination Management Organization (DMO) nell'ambito del Piano di Sviluppo Turistico della Grecia Salentina

The DMO related to the consortium of municipalities part of the Grecia Salentina territory is being defined, through which a coordinated, sustainable and virtuous management of sites of interest and attraction, human capital and environmental resources is to be pursued, in order to increase, promote and enhance the value of tourist flows related to the territory.

Among the main drivers envisaged are local agri-food productions, practices, knowledge, techniques, cultural and linguistic distinctiveness (griko) that represent a social glue and identity reference for communities.

To this end, a fruitful dialogue has been initiated with local tour operators to devise and test new experiences, attractions and services that qualify and satisfy visitors' cultural demand. This will include the development of new tourist itineraries, the creation of widespread events, and the activation of sustainability training courses for local stakeholders.

To date, finally, a network of local food and beverage operators is being set up, who will be the recipients of a training proposal aimed at encouraging and developing their narrative skills in relation to the food and wine culture of the country and their respective territorial contexts in order to increase their tourist attractiveness, but in the first instance their awareness. Currently, the format has been developed and submitted to local stakeholders, specifically represented in the restaurant sector, who took part in the conference organized on April 30, 2024 at the Palazzo Marchesale in Melpignano (LE), entitled "Food as a strategic lever for the tourism development of Grecìa Salentina (fig. 15). Restaurants as cultural garrisons." It was a public meeting addressed to restaurateurs of the area and mayors of the Union of Municipalities of the Grecìa Salentina to implement innovative actions on food and territorial identity as strategic assets in promotion and development processes.

A promotional poster for a conference. At the top, logos for 'Grecìa Salentina', 'Unione dei Comuni della Grecìa Salentina', 'Università del Salento', 'Italiadomani', 'NODES', and 'Presidio Food' are displayed. The main title reads: "IL cibo come leva strategica per lo sviluppo turistico della Grecìa Salentina. Ristoranti come presidi culturali". Below this, the event details are listed: "30 APRILE ORE 17:00 PALAZZO MARCHESALE MELPIGNANO". The central graphic features a hand holding a golden tray with a map of the Grecìa Salentina region on it, while another hand pours a golden liquid from a golden pitcher onto the map. The bottom text describes the event as a public meeting for restaurateurs and local stakeholders, organized by the University of Salento and the Union of Municipalities of the Grecìa Salentina, to discuss innovative actions on food and territorial identity as strategic assets for promotion and development.

UNIONE DEI COMUNI DELLA GRECÌA SALENTINA

UNIVERSITÀ DEL SALENTO

Italiadomani

NODES

PRESIDIO FOOD

IL cibo come LEVA STRATEGICA PER LO *sviluppo turistico* DELLA GRECÌA SALENTINA. RISTORANTI COME PRESIDII CULTURALI

30 APRILE
ORE 17:00
PALAZZO MARCHESALE
MELPIGNANO

Incontro pubblico rivolto alle ristoratrici e i ristoratori del territorio con il Rettore dell'Università del Salento e i Sindaci dell'Unione dei Comuni della Grecìa Salentina per implementare azioni innovative su cibo e identità territoriale quali asset strategici nei processi di promozione e sviluppo.

Fig. 15 - "Il cibo come leva strategica per lo sviluppo turistico della Grecìa Salentina. Ristoranti come presidi culturali" (Melpignano, April 30, 2024)

3. Conclusion

The period under review (October 2024-May 2024), has seen, therefore, the University of Salento research group engaged on several project fronts, united by the theme of intangible cultural heritage as an engine of territorial development. The work, however, focused primarily on the analysis of the economic, social and cultural potential arising from the enhancement of local agri-food resources and the promotion of a short and sustainable supply chain.

The territories involved in various capacities in the different projects are clearly characterized by a rich and ancient agricultural and food and wine tradition, but they face daily challenges related to loss of cultural identity, rural desertification and lack of real economic opportunities. Therefore, there is a need for food to be identified -- first and foremost among local public and private communities and stakeholders- as a key element in revitalizing the local economy and promoting sustainable development, including cultural and social development.

Objectives in the coming months will certainly include the provision of an interim analysis and comparison phase between the different case studies addressed, which will be the "core competence" of the Nodes project, as well as the creation and strengthening of networks between producers, restaurateurs and consumers and the implementation of a series of actions aimed at raising community awareness of the importance of adopting sustainable agrifood development models. Therefore, meetings will be organized with agricultural producers, restaurateurs, local authorities, and community members to share visions, knowledge, and ideas; public events, training tracks, and workshops to engage the community and spread the culture of sustainable food as a genuine driver of local development. Finally, it is essential to integrate policies to promote local traditions and typical food and wine with virtuous, long-term territorial development plans.